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ON FARM EVALUATION OF POTENTIAL BIO-PRODUCTS AGAINST COLLAR ROT CAUSED BY *SCLEROTIUM ROLFSSII* SACC. IN BRINJAL

Divya.S ^{1*} and Datchina Murthy.K ²

1. ICAR-Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Karaikal, UT of Puducherry.
2. PQS, Government of India, Trichy, Tamil Nadu

*Corresponding Author Email: divyakvkkaraikal@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

Field experiments were carried out during Rabi 2023-24 at Agalankannu village and Pettai village of Karaikal District, U.T. of Puducherry to compare the efficacy of different Bio-products against Collar rot Management in Brinjal. It was found that among the treatments (T1) Treating the seeds with *Trichoderma asperellum* @ 4 g / kg of seeds 24 hours before sowing and soil application of *Bacillus subtilis* @ 2.5 kg/ha with 50 kg of FYM was effective and significantly reduced the collar rot incidence with 4.29 per cent disease incidence with highest yield of 191.6 q/ha, followed by 11.55 per cent disease incidence with yield of 173.4 q/ha for (T2) Seed Treatment with Arka Microbial Consortium (AMC) @ 20 g/100 g of seed and before transplanting root dipping with 20 g/lit carried out in the main field and soil application of 5 kg of AMC with 500 kg of FYM and applied near the root zone of standing crop and AMC was mixed with water @ 20 g/ lit and then applied near to the root zone on the 10th day after transplanting and 41.49 for farmer practices (T3) only application of chemical fungicides carbendazim or carbendazim plus Mancozeb combination fungicide after the disease incidence respectively. Increased Net Return of Rs. 3, 89,047/ha with a benefit cost ratio of 1:3.08 in T1 and whereas it was Rs. 3,24,440/- with a benefit cost ratio of 1: 2.61 for T2 and in (T3) farmers practices it was Rs. 1,56,927/ha, with a benefit cost ratio of 1: 1.52 respectively in farmers practices.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Brinjal is grown on nearly 5,50,000 hectares in India, making the country the second largest producer after China with a 26% world production share (www.isaaa.org). Brinjal crop is grown in Rabi season in Karaikal District, Union Territory of Pudhucherry. Poiyur brinjal variety is one of the major variety grown by farmers in Karaikal region. Brinjal color rot is one of the major diseases of brinjal and causes huge yield loss. Collar rot (*Sclerotium rolfsii*) requires warm climate, high moisture and high temperature (Singh et al., 2023). The *Sclerotium rolfsii* is a soil borne pathogen, during the favourable condition it become active. The disease is found to be severe in the tropical and subtropical region where temperature is high which favours the growth of pathogen (Maria and Udhayakumar, 2021). The collar rot/wilt disease caused by *Sclerotium rolfsii* is an important constraint in brinjal production (Lokesh and Kantharaju, 2018). Among the soil borne fungal diseases, collar rot has become one of the constraints resulting in yield losses up to 16-30 per cent (Singh and Dhancholia, 1991). Eggplant receive the maximum pesticide spray after chilli in India (Kodandaram et al., 2013). Though several chemical fungicides available for management of the disease, an attempt has been made to evaluate effective ecofriendly management options for the collar rot management.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted at Pettai, and Agalangannu villages of Karaikal District during 2023-24 under irrigated condition in order to assess the efficacy of different bio-products towards the management of Collar rot of brinjal. Three treatments were imposed, T1: Treating the seeds

with *Trichoderma asperellum* @ 4 g / kg of seeds 24 hours before sowing and soil application of *Bacillus subtilis* @ 2.5 kg/ha with 50 kg of FYM. T2: Seed treatment with Arka Microbial Consortium (AMC) @ 20 g/100 g of seed and before transplanting root dipping with 20 g/lit carried out in the main field and soil application of 5 kg of AMC with 500 kg of FYM (Fig.1) and applied near the root zone of standing crop and AMC was mixed with water @ 20 g/ lit and then applied near to the root zone on the 10th day after transplanting and the T3: Farmers practices only application of chemical fungicides carbendazim or carbendazim plus Mancozeb combination fungicide after the disease incidence. In all five replicated fields incidence of collar rot disease was recorded on 30, 60 and 90 Days After Transplanting (DAT). Five separate locations within a field were used to calculate the disease incidence in a square meter area. The disease incidence was calculated based on the infected and total numbers of plants. The percent disease incidence was calculated by using the formula.

$$\text{PDI} = \frac{\text{No. of Plants affected}}{\text{Total number of plants observed}} \times 100$$

The data so obtained was then analyzed by Randomized Block Design (RBD) through ANOVA technique (Gomez and Gomez, 1984).

Fig:1.Demo on Soil Application of *Bacillus subtilis* and Arka Microbial Consortium

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

A field Experiment were conducted to evaluate the efficacy of different bio-products against brinjal collar rot during Rabi season 2023-24. The results revealed that the collar rot incidence recorded were 1.56, 2.97 and 15.84 PDI of Collar rot incidence on 30 DAT and where as it was 2.34, 5.46 and 22.38 on 60 DAT and it was 4.29, 11.55 and 41.49 DAT on 90 DAT in T1,T2 and T3 respectively (Table.1). This study agreed with those of Veerendra Kuar and Saju George. 2018. Drenching of Peper vines with AMC@ 20 g/lit three times in a year performed significantly better in terms of reduction in leaf yellowing, collar infection incidence and wilting of vines.

Table.1: Efficacy of Bioproducts on Collar rot in Brinjal

Treatments	Percent Collar rot incidence in Brinjal		
	(PDI)		
	30 DAT	60 DAT	90 DAT
T1	1.56	2.34	4.29
T2	2.97	5.46	11.55
T3	15.84	22.38	41.49
S.Ed ±	1.54	1.67	2.52
C.D. (p=0.05)	3.03	4.17	6.15
C.V. (%)	14.45	26.11	48.29

Table.2: Economics of different collar rot management modules in Brinjal

Treatment	Yield (q/ha)	Gross Cost (Rs.)	Gross Return (Rs.)	Net Return (Rs.)	B:C
T 1	191.6	186953	576000	389047	1: 3.08
T 2	173.4	201760	526200	324440	1: 2.61
T 3	152.6	300873	457800	1,56,927	1: 1.52

In the present study the effect of Bio-products on yield was reported in Table 2. The results revealed that the yield was the maximum (191.6 q /ha) in T1 followed by T2 (173.4 q/ha) and whereas (152.6 q/ha) in 3 (farmers field). As the farmers practice depends heavily on the usage of fungicides the cost per spray will be around Rs. 18,000/ha hence for six spray costs Rs. 45,000/- to Rs. 50,000/- for the management of collar rot. Whereas it was Rs.4,500/ha and Rs. 6,000/ha in T1 and T2 respectfully. The cost of cultivation and net return per hectare in treatment fields were Rs. 1,86,953/- and Rs.3,89,047/- for T1 whereas Rs.2,01,760 /- and Rs. 3,24,440/- in T2 and in T3 it was Rs. 3,00,873/- and Rs. 1,56,927/- and benefit cost ratio of T1, T2 and T3 was 1: 3.08, 1: 2.61 and 1:1.52 respectively. Our present results revealed that following to Arka Microbial Consortium Seed treatment with *Trichoderma viride* and soil application with *Bacillus subtilis* also effective in the management of Collar rot of Brinjal comparing to the chemical treatment are also in agreement with earlier studies by Sain et al. 2023 revealed that the combined application of the most effective strains of *T. asperillum* (Th-11) @ 10 g/kg + *P. fluorescens* @ 10 g/kg and AMF @ 20 g/kg can effectively manage mango root rot and wilt disease up to 60 days after sowing and enhance plant growth under field conditions in Cotton cultivation. Similar finding was also reported by Hiremath and Nagaraju (2009) also found similar results of *Trichoderma viride* application for disease management. Present findings are in accordance with earlier results of (Ruthy Tabing and Shashi Tiwari. 2018) who found that brinjal collar rot can be effectively managed by soil treatment and seedling root dip treatment with bio-agent viz. *Trichoderma viride*, *Pseudomonas* and *Bacillus*, botanicals viz. neem oil and eucalyptus oil, cow urine and soil amendment with mustard cake. These results are consistent with the studies by Mool Chand Meena *et al.* 2019 that Bio-agents are eco-friendly, cost effective free from environmental pollution and very effective in controlling of stem rot disease as compared to other methods. Similar results was obtained for

Vishal *et al.* 2017. that in case of bioagents, *Pseudomonas* gave maximum sunflower collar rot control (55.11 %) on an average followed by *T. harzianum* (51.35%) on an average in both hybrids. Further, in this study disease incidence was recorded less in bioagents compared to chemical treated. This is because chemical fungicides are treated by farmers only after the disease occurrence with in the time many plants will be severely affected and leads to death of the plant. But in case of Bio-agents seed treatment and soil application before planting builds immunity to the plant and act as additional protection.

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